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Research Article

**QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF MORINGA OLEIFERA LEAVES
EXTRACT BY USING DIFFERENT ANALYTICAL
TECHNIQUES****¹Baratam Sandhya Rani, ²Uppada Harini, ³Mutchumari Jahnvi, ⁴Palla Triveni,
⁵Vanapalli Dihitha, ⁶Behara Mohan, ⁷Kakarlamudi Laxmi Deepak**¹ Associate Professor, Raghu College of Pharmacy, Dakamarri, Visakhapatnam-531162² Associate Professor, Raghu College of Pharmacy, Dakamarri, Visakhapatnam-531162^{3,4,5,6,7} Student, Raghu College of Pharmacy, Dakamarri, Visakhapatnam-531162**Abstract:**

Moringa oleifera lam, a traditional medicinal plant that has many properties like anti- inflammatory, anti-oxidant and many more. This plant is native to the Indian subcontinent and used extensively in south and southeast Asia. As these are abundant and has many useful properties, usage of the plant for the medicinal purpose is necessary by the mankind. The extraction method for the plants like maceration, Soxhlet extraction methods for extracting the greater quality of extract with main phytochemical constituents is necessary. The solvents like methanol, ethanol and others also play an important role for the extraction method. The presence or absence of various metabolites should be known in order to know various properties. This can be done by phytochemical screening for the extract. This study shows anti-bacterial activity for the extract prepared. The constituents present in the extract can be known by using analytical techniques like UV-Visible spectroscopy and High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography by comparing it with the standards. This study further discusses about the future scope of the drug material.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera extract, phytochemical constituents, Anti-bacterial activity, UV-Visible spectroscopy, High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography, Soxhlet extraction.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Moringa oleifera Lam, it is commonly called as drumstick or moringa. It is a medicinal plant from the family Moringaceae. It is an abundant plant available in many countries of the tropics and subtropics. The *M. oleifera* has various medicinal benefits for almost all of its parts of the plant^[6]. Horseradish tree, ben oil tree, miracle tree, and mother's best friend are some other names for moringa^[2].

Origin and geography:

In this genus moringa of Moringaceae family has 13 more species in which *Moringa oleifera* is the mostly used species for the studies. It is a fast growing; its wood is soft and the tree can reach to 12 m height. It can treat up to 300 diseases said by the ayurvedic traditional medicine. The leaves of the species are both preventive and curative purposed. The plant growth in tropics and subtropics with annual precipitation of 760 to 2500 mm mostly and temperature between 18 and 28 degrees centigrade in any soil type. At altitude 2000m with pH 4.5 and 8 in heavy clay type the growth is possible^[7].

Botanical description of the *Moringa oleifera*:

Moringa oleifera is the soft wood tree where bark is deeply fissured, young parts tomentose, thick, soft, corky. Leaves are tri-pinnate, leaflets are elliptic, flowers are white in colour, smell is fragrant, in large panicles. Pods are pendulous, green in colour, triangle shaped and ribbed. Seeds are trigonous with wings on angles^[8].

Pharmacological activities:

- Hypercholesterolemic
- Anti diabetic
- Immunity booster^[24]
- Hypertensive agent
- Regulate thyroid hormone
- Gastric ulcers
- Scurvy
- Hepatoprotective
- Anti tubercular
- Anti-tumour
- Diuretic
- Anti pyretic
- Analgesic
- Antiepileptic
- Anti spasmodic^[9]

The above mentioned are some common activities for the plant but unique characteristics are present for different parts of the plant that include root bark of the

plant has antiviral, anti-inflammatory, analgesic characters. Cardiotonic, stimulant, diuretic properties are seen in the flowers. Anti-oxidant property is significant and seen in leaves, seeds, pods. In leaves antioxidant property is more significant due to presence of secondary metabolites like phenols and flavonoids^[10,23]. The plant includes various phytoconstituents like alkaloids, phenols etc. and minerals like iron, potassium, calcium, copper, zinc, magnesium, manganese etc...^[15]

Antioxidant activity:

The mature and tender leaves extract of moringa have potent antioxidant property where it gives protection against free radicals from damaging the biomolecules from oxidation. The phenolic content present in the moringa oleifera is responsible for the antioxidant function. However, high amounts of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, tannins are present in the hydroalcoholic leaf extract^[11,21].

Wound healing activity:

There are various types of wounds where ethanolic leaf extract and ethyl acetate leaf extract have more wound healing property. Comparatively ethyl acetate leaf extract has more wound healing capacity^[11].

Anti diabetic activity:

Moringa drops the blood sugar level within three hours on consumption of the leaf extract, but is less successful than hypoglycemic drugs^[11].

Uses of *Moringa oleifera*:

- Leaf extract is antioxidant and boost the immunity.
- Leaves are grinded into powder used as additives in salads, soups, sauces etc..
- Leaf and pods extract used to stimulate appetite
- Helps in digestion
- Scurvy, flatulence, catarrh are treated in offsprings by tender leaves
- Leaf juice is used by the patients suffering from cancer, ulcer, inflammations, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, insulin resistance, asthma, depression, epilepsy, convulsion, oxidative stress, infertility, obesity, colitis, dysentery, diarrhoea, diabetes, gonorrhoea
- Used to expel intestinal worms
- Antiseptic agent for skin diseases.

The seed powder of moringa is used in the water

treatment acts as natural coagulant and also used as laxative. Crushed leaves are used as home cleaning agents^[12].

Phyto-chemical constituents of *Moringa oleifera* plant:

Most of the constituents are present in the leaves of the moringa and are grouped as follows:

- Vitamins: vitamin A, vitamin B1, vitamin B2, vitamin B3, vitamin C, vitamin E.
- Polyphenols.
- Phenolic acids: caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid, o- coumaric acid, p-coumaric acid, ellagic acid, ferulic acid, gallic acid, Gentistic acid, Sinapic acid, syringic acid.
- Flavonoids: apigenin, daidzein, epicatechin, genistein, isorhamnetin, kaempferol, myricetin, quercetin, rutin.
- Glucosinolates: Benzyl, 4-hydroxybenzyl.
- Alkaloids: α -L-rhamnopyranosyl vincosamide, 4-(α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy) phenylacetone nitrile (niazirin), pyrrolemarumine 4''-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside, 4'hydroxy phenylethanamide- α -L-rhamnopyranoside (marumosi A) and its 3-O- β -Glucopyranosyl-derivative (marumosi B) and methyl 4-(α -L- rhamnopyranosyloxy) benzylcarbamate.
- Carotenoids: lutein, beta- carotene, zeaxanthin. • Anthocyanins
- Tannins.
- Saponins.
- Oxalates and phytates.

Other constituents present in seeds such as

- Fatty acids: arachidic acid, octacosanoic acid, oleic acid, palmitic acid^[7].

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Materials and Methods:

Drugs:

- a. *Moringa oleifera* leaves
- b. Ethanol
- c. Quercetin (standard)
- d. Rutin (standard)
- e. Toluene
- f. Ethyl acetate
- g. Glacial acetic acid

Instruments:

- a. Soxhlet apparatus
- b. UV cabinet
- c. UV- Visible spectrophotometer (LAB INDIA)

- d. High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (CAMAG Linomat 5)
- e. Analytical balance (Shimadzu)

Collection of plant material: [leaves]:

Fresh leaves were collected from the surrounding living areas randomly. According to families, plants were identified and studied. After collecting leaves are washed with tap water and allowed for shade drying and then ground into fine powder and stored in an air tight container.

Preparation of leaves extract:

- Fresh leaves of *Moringa oleifera* were collected, washed to get rid of dust particles
- The leaves are shade dried for about 15 days at room temperature and then powdered into fine powdered.
- 10g of dried leaf powder of the plant was extracted with the help of Soxhlet apparatus using solvent ethanol.
- After colour changes the extract was collected and filtered.
- The excess solvent is removed from the filtrate.
- Process is repeated until the plant material is completely extracted
- Phyto-chemical screening was performed for the collected extract to identify the chemical constituents and extract product was run for the analysis UV-VIS Spectroscopy, TLC (Thin layer chromatography) and HPTLC (High performance thin layer chromatography)^[13,14,15].

SET UP FOR THE SOXHLET EXTRACTION:

- For the Soxhlet extraction Soxhlet apparatus and a heating mantle are required as shown in fig-9.
- 100ml of solvent is taken in the round bottom flask and 10g of leaf powder was placed in thimble of Soxhlet apparatus.
- Condenser was fixed to the Soxhlet apparatus and water was run.
- Then the Soxhlet extraction is started, the temperature is adjusted in heating mantle.
- The extract is collected after the colour change.

Phyto-chemical analysis of *moringa oleifera* leaf extract:

1. Test for alkaloid:
WAGNER'S TEST: To the sample add a drop of Wagner's reagent. The presence of alkaloids indicates the reddish-brown precipitate^[2].
2. Test for tannins:
To the sample add 10ml of water in the test tube

and add few drops of ferric chloride. Presence of tannins shows brownish green or blue- black coloration^[3].

3. Test for cardiac glycosides:

To the sample add few ml of water and then add few ml of glacial acetic acid and one drop of $FeCl_3$ and it was added with conc. sulphuric acid. Brown ring was formed at the interface indicates the presence of cardiac glycosides^[4].

4. Test for flavonoids:

Few ml of dil. Ammonia solution is added to extract and then followed by conc. Sulphuric acid. Yellow coloration indicates the presence of flavonoids^[4].

5. Test for reducing sugars:

FEHLINGS TEST: To the extract add equal amounts of Fehling's solution A & B and then boil the solution in the water bath. The presence of reducing sugars indicates the formation of brick red precipitate^[2].

6. Test for carbohydrates:

MOLISCH TEST: To the extract add 1ml of Molisch reagent through the side of the test tube. Purple or reddish violet colour at the junction indicates the presence of carbohydrates^[1].

7. Test for terpenoids/steroids:

SALKOWSKI TEST: To the sample extract add few ml of chloroform and about 3ml of conc. H_2SO_4 . brown coloration at the interface indicates the presence of terpenoids and steroids^[2].

8. Test for proteins or amino acids:

BIURET TEST: Add few drops of NaOH and few drops of $CuSO_4$ and then add few ml of extract to the test tube. Formation of the pinkish or violet colour shows the presence of proteins^[1].

9. Test for saponins:

FOAM FORMATION TEST/ FROTHING TEST: Extract was added to the test tube with distilled water and shaken vigorously. Presence of stable persistent foam indicates the presence of saponins^[5].

10. Test for anthraquinone glycosides:

To the extract in the test tube add dil. Sulphuric acid and boiled. Cooled and filtered, add few ml of benzene and then add ammonia of few drops. Ammoniacal layer separated indicates.

Anti-bacterial studies:

Preparation of standard samples:

1. Preparation of Quercetin: Standard sample of quercetin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of quercetin in 10ml of ethanol.

2. Preparation of Rutin: Standard sample of Rutin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of rutin in 10ml of ethanol.

Preparation of the samples (Soxhlet extract):

- The ethanolic extract of *Moringa oleifera* is filtered and used for the anti- microbial studies.

Anti-bacterial activity:

- The activity was performed by using agar cup plate method.
- The anti-bacterial activity of the extract was compared with the standards Rutin and Quercetin solutions of 1000 μ g/ml concentration.
- The antimicrobial activity was analysed by comparing the zone of inhibition against various organisms.
- The following test organisms are used

Test organisms:

1. Gram positive bacteria: *Bacillus subtilis*^[21]
2. Gram negative bacteria: *Escherichia coli*^[19]

Procedure:

- Agar medium was prepared by using agar(2gm), peptone(0.5mg), sodium chloride(0.5mg), Beef extract (0.3) dissolved in distilled water of 100ml in a conical flask.
- The prepared medium was autoclaved at 121 $^{\circ}$ C for 20 minutes at 15lb pressure for sterilization.
- The medium was inoculated using 18hrs old culture of the above mentioned test organisms.
- Then it was poured into sterile petri plates and allowed to set in the room temperature for about 30min.
- 4 cups were made at equal distance in each petri plate.
- One cup was used for test compound i.e. extract of 1000 μ g/ml concentration. Other cup is used for control i.e ethanol solvent. The other two cups are used for each standard.
- The plates are left for about 90 min for diffusion. The plates were kept for incubation for 24hrs at 37 $^{\circ}$ C.
- After incubation, the plates were taken out and calculated for zone of inhibition.^[18]

Estimation by UV- Visible spectroscopy:

Preparation of standard samples:

1. Preparation of Quercetin: Standard sample of quercetin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of

quercetin in 10ml of ethanol. Dilution solution was prepared from the above solution of concentration 100µg/ml.

2. Preparation of Rutin: Standard sample of Rutin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of rutin in 10ml of ethanol. Dilution solution was prepared from the above solution of 100µg/ml concentration.

Preparation of the samples (Soxhlet extract)

- The collected extract is filtered and used for the analysis of the sample.
- Dilution solution was prepared from the above solution of concentration 100µg/ml.
- The solutions are analysed by using ethanol as the blank.

Selection of wavelength for analysis: The solutions were scanned in the range of 200-800nm using UV-Vis Spectrophotometer.^[10,26]

Estimation by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)

Preparation of standard samples:

1. Preparation of Quercetin: Standard sample of quercetin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of quercetin in 10ml of ethanol. Dilution solution was prepared from the above solution of concentration 100µg/ml.
2. Preparation of Rutin: Standard sample of Rutin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of rutin in 10ml of ethanol. Dilution solution was prepared from the above solution of concentration 100µg/ml.

Optimised mobile phase:

- Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Ethanol: Glacial acetic acid (2:1.5:2:0.5)

Procedure:

- Precoated silica gel plates are used for the thin layer chromatography.
- The required mobile phase is prepared and allowed for saturation.
- The spots of the extract and standard samples are spotted on the plates by using capillary tube.
- The plate is allowed to place in the mobile phase chamber and allowed the solvent to run through.
- After the solvent run for 75% the plate is removed from the chamber and allowed to dry.

- The plate is observed in the UV cabinet for the clear view of the spots.
- The Rf values is calculated for the extract spots and standard spots.^[27]

Estimation by High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC)

Preparation of standard samples:

1. Preparation of Quercetin: Standard sample of quercetin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of quercetin in 10ml of ethanol.
2. Preparation of Rutin: Standard sample of Rutin is prepared by dissolving 10mg of rutin in 10ml of ethanol.
3. The dilution solution of 100µg/ml concentration each is prepared from the above standard samples.

Preparation of the sample:

- The extract is filtered and the stock solution is prepared by using ethanol as the solvent.
- The dilution solution of 100µg/ml concentration is prepared from the above stock solution

Preparation of the mobile phase

- Toluene of 11.5 ml, ethyl acetate of 11.5ml, ethanol of 11.5ml and glacial acetic acid of 5.6 ml is measured and poured into twin trough chamber.

Procedure:

- The instructions are given to the software as per requirements.
- Precoated silica gel plates are used for the high-performance thin layer chromatography.^[27]
- The required mobile phase is prepared and allowed for saturation.
- The spotting of the samples is done by the instrument as per the software directions.
- The plate is allowed to place in the mobile phase chamber and allowed the solvent to run through.
- After the solvent run for 75% the plate is removed from the chamber and allowed to dry.
- The plate is observed in the UV cabinet for the clear view of the spots.
- The spots on the plate are detected and the peaks, Rf values etc.. are shown in the read out device.^[6,16]

Chromatographic conditions:

Spray gas	- Inert gas
Sample solvent type	- Ethanol
Chamber type	- Twin trough chamber 20×10cm
Mobile phase	- Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Ethanol: Glacial acetic acid (11.5:11.5:11.5:5.6)
Temperature	- 60°C
Time	- 5mins
Wavelength	- 254nm
Lamp	- D2 & W

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Phytochemical screening**

The study carried out shows some of the active chemical constituents by performing the above tests. The ethanolic extract of leaves of moringa shows presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, reducing sugars, steroids, saponins and anthraquinone glycosides and absence of carbohydrates, proteins and cardiac glycosides. The further results were shown in the table below

Table-1:Phytochemical screening

TEST	RESULT
Test for alkaloids	Positive
Test for tannins	Positive
Test for cardiac glycosides	Negative
Test for flavonoids	Positive
Test for reducing sugars	Positive
Test for carbohydrates	Negative
Test for terpenoids/ steroids	Positive
Test for proteins or amino acids	Negative
Test for saponins	Positive
Test for anthraquinone glycosides	Positive

Anti-bacterial studies

The zone of inhibition was calculated for each sample in the plates and recorded. The zone of inhibition of the extract for both the bacteria was found to be same i.e. 15mm. The results for the standards are shown in the tables below

Table-2: *Moringa oleifera* extract

BACTERIA	ZONE OF INHIBITION	AREA OF INHIBITION
E.COLI	15mm	706.85mm ²
B.S	15mm	706.85mm ²

Table-3: Standard Rutin

BACTERIA	ZONE OF INHIBITION	AREA OF INHIBITION
E.COLI	17.5mm	962.11mm ²
B.S	11mm	380.13mm ²

Table-4: Standard Quercetin

BACTERIA	ZONE INHIBITION	OF	AREA OF INHIBITION	OF
E.COLI	12.5mm		490.87mm ²	
B.S	17mm		907.92mm ²	

Estimation by UV-Visible Spectroscopy

The analysis carried out shows absorbance for the extract and the standard solutions at various wavelengths. The absorbance was seen between the wavelength of 200-800 nm. The maximum absorbance for the sample and standard solutions at certain wavelengths are shown in the tables

Fig-1: *Moringa oleifera* extract

Fig-2: Standard Quercetin

Fig-3: Standard Rutin

Fig-4: *Moringa oleifera* extract, Rutin, Quercetin

Table-5: UV-Visible Spectroscopy

S.NO	SAMPLE	WAVELENGHT MAXIMA
1	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> extract	438.0, 562.0, 701.0nm
2	Quercetin	418.0nm
3	Rutin	430.0nm

Estimation by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)

Estimation by TLC shows the presence of some of the compounds in the extract. The Rf values are calculated and recorded as shown below

Rf = distance travelled by solute/ distance travelled by solvent

Table-6: Thin layer chromatography

S.NO	SAMPLE	Rf VALUES
1	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> extract	0.82 , 0.95
2	Quercetin	0.79
3	Rutin	0.92

Fig-5: Quercetin, *Moringa oleifera* extract and Rutin**Estimation by High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC)**

The chromatogram uses mobile phase of toluene: ethyl acetate: ethanol: glacial acetic acid shows peaks at the wavelength 254nm for extract dilution, rutin dilution, quercetin dilution and the Rf values for the solutions and further results are shown in the tables below

Fig-6: Wavelength scan for all the samples

Fig-7: *Moringa oleifera* extract dilution(100µg/ml)

Fig-8: Standard Quercetin dilution(100µg/ml)

Fig-9:Standard Rutin dilution (100µg/ml)

Table-7: *Moringa oleifera* extract dilution

PEAK	Rf	AREA	% AREA
1	0.57	7692.5	94.06
2	0.62	218.0	2.67
3	0.65	267.4	3.27

Table-8: Quercetin dilution

PEAK	Rf	AREA	% AREA
1	0.58	11887.4	98.57
2	0.61	172.8	1.43

Table-9: Rutin dilution

PEAK	Rf	AREA	% AREA
1	0.58	10862.9	97.40
2	0.61	289.9	2.60

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

This study demonstrated the analytical techniques, antimicrobial properties, and phytochemical composition of *Moringa oleifera*. The phytochemical screening revealed the presence of various beneficial compounds, supporting its traditional use in medicine. The phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of diverse beneficial compounds, including flavonoids, phenolics, and alkaloids which may contribute to its antimicrobial properties. The antimicrobial studies demonstrated significant inhibitory activity against a range of microorganisms. UV-Visible spectroscopy analysis revealed characteristic absorption patterns, indicating the presence of specific phytoconstituents. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) and High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC) fingerprinting enabled the separation, identification, and quantification of bioactive. These findings validate the traditional medicinal applications of *Moringa oleifera* and suggest its potential use in developing novel

antimicrobial formulations. From the study we can conclude that *Moringa oleifera* has different pharmacological activities like antidiabetic, hypertensive agent, regulate thyroid hormone, CNS, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, increases immunity etc.

FUTURE SCOPE

1. Phytochemical characterization
2. Pharmacological studies
3. Clinical trails
4. Quality control and assurance
5. Safety monitoring

By leveraging advanced analytical techniques and technologies, the future of herbal medicines holds much promise for improving human health and well-being.

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